

DATA EVALUATION IN ACADEMIA: IMPLEMENTATION GUIDE

'Implementing data
evaluation in academia'
Working Group

makedatacount.org/explore-resources/institutions/

Contents

This guide, developed by the '[Implementing Data Evaluation in Academia](#)' Working Group*, provides practical guidance for integrating open scholarship into institutional review processes. It supports institutions, researchers, and review committees in recognizing data and other open outputs as integral to research assessment. The guide is organized into three sections:

1. Sample language for tenure and promotion policies
2. A researcher CV template
3. Guidance for review committees and external reviewers

*The '[Implementing Data Evaluation in Academia](#)' Working Group is a collaboration between [Make Data Count](#) and [HELIOS Open](#) that focuses on supporting the inclusion of data evaluation in institutional processes.

01

Tenure & Promotion Policies

Sample Language

This section contains sample text that may be included in policy documents to signal recognition of data contributions and open scholarship practices. Institutions are encouraged to adapt and extend the examples as appropriate to their needs. The article [‘Ten simple rules for recognizing data and software contributions in hiring, promotion, and tenure’](#) provides further guidance and considerations for recognizing data and software in institutional processes.

Research productivity and open scholarship

Our institution recognizes research practices designed to make research more reliable, rigorous, and aligned to open scholarship. The evaluation process is transparent and values the broad spectrum of research products that researchers produce and openly share as part of their research. When describing their research productivity, faculty are encouraged to document and share open datasets, software, workflows, protocols, code, and other scholarly products that contribute to research transparency, accessibility, and impact, alongside traditional research outputs such as journal publications.

Assessments of research productivity at our institution incorporate attributes related to open data and open research outputs, such as those below:

- Creation or curation of datasets that are shared openly to the extent that this is ethically and legally possible.
- Creation and open sharing of research or analysis tools, workflows, software or code.
- Creation of resources for facilitating research, such as data collections, or platforms for hosting and/or interacting with large datasets to facilitate collaborative research. This also includes platforms to interact with closed data that cannot be shared in their raw form due to privacy or ethical concerns.

Open scholarship practices

Faculty who adopt open scholarship practices – including data management and sharing, open access publications and preprints, open methods and workflows (e.g., preregistration), open educational materials, and open code – are recognized for their contributions to scientific rigor and reproducibility.

Assessment of research contributions

The evaluation of research contributions includes consideration toward evidence of adherence to community standards for open and reproducible scholarship, complete reporting of activities across the research cycle (e.g. via preregistration and adherence to reporting guidelines) and the development and open sharing (where ethically and legally permitted) of research tools, instruments, code, and data.

Evaluators consider the time, complexity, and collaborative nature of producing high-quality reusable datasets and data infrastructures. This includes curating, maintaining, and sharing datasets ethically and sustainably. Evaluators may also want to recognize contributions that enhance accessibility in research, particularly work that addresses the specific needs of underrepresented communities.

Research that involves the use of existing datasets or collections of datasets is also considered, and researchers are encouraged to discuss these approaches and how they relate to practices in their field in their personal statements for consideration by the evaluators.

Evaluation of potential for impact

The evaluation of the potential for impact of the research contributions can be informed by a wide range of indicators that span beyond traditional publication metrics. Indicators of potential for impact may include quantitative measures, contextual information, and qualitative evidence. Such indicators may include:

- Complete reporting of results and open sharing of research outputs associated with published articles, through preregistrations, open data, code and/or materials
- Counts of open datasets and other open outputs
- Citations to data, software or preregistrations
- Dataset views and downloads
- Software downloads and installs
- Use of the data, software or open outputs in projects, activities, or collaborations that advanced understanding in the field or addressed knowledge gaps
- Evidence of adherence to community standards for open scholarship (e.g. FAIR principles) and standards for conducting ethically sound and reproducible research
- Evidence of community engagement or endorsement of the open data or other open outputs developed

The outline of the potential for impact for the research contributions can take a narrative format where the researcher provides a contextualized description of their key data and open outputs and how they advanced the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies or knowledge. This outline can include a description of the pathways to impact that the researcher envisions for their data and open outputs, including possible future reuses that might advance research endeavours, spur innovation, or bring societal benefit.

02

Researcher CV Format

Annotated Data-Friendly Template

Annotated CV entries help reviewers understand the significance of non-traditional outputs by providing context that citation counts alone cannot capture. The content of CVs vary from discipline to discipline but, in the sciences and humanities especially, have typically focused on documenting traditional research outputs which are static or narrative in nature such as books, journal articles, and conference papers. However, scholarly outputs take many forms and non-traditional outputs can be as impactful as traditional ones, although the metrics between, for example, peer-reviewed articles and research code may differ. Outputs such as research data, code, web-based interactive outputs, and so on may need additional information or annotation in a CV in order to accurately reflect the work and its impact.

Some style guides (e.g. APA, MLA) as well as publishers and scholarly societies now include format guidelines for citing such works that can be adapted for CVs and can serve as a good guide for researchers. Additionally, some institutions have shared example CV guides or templates that illustrate ways to organize and annotate CVs, c.f. [Stanford Medicine's example](#) or the [annotated CV format](#) developed at the University of Maryland.

When including research data and code as research outputs in a CV, researchers may wish to create a separate section for these outputs or include them alongside related traditional outputs. In either case, researchers are encouraged to use an annotated approach that includes as many of the following as reasonably possible:

- Type of Output: e.g., Dataset, Software, Protocol, Workflow, Tool, Model
- Persistent Identifier: e.g., DOI, ORCID-linked entry
- Authorship Role: e.g., data collector, curator, analyst from [CRediT](#), or other data roles e.g., data modeling, transformation
- Data Type: e.g., longitudinal, experimental, observational, qualitative, simulation
- Availability: e.g., openly available under CC0 license; restricted due to ethical reasons
- Use and Reuse: e.g., number of downloads, citations, mentions in other research or activities
- Statement of Contribution: A short paragraph describing the unique contribution, innovations, or community value of the research product.

Resources to support development of annotated CV entries for datasets

You may find additional resources on how to cite datasets or retrieve usage metrics for datasets on the [Make Data Count website](#) or through the resources below:

Data citation format: The [DataCite Commons](#) portal includes records for datasets with DOIs and citation formats in different styles.

Data citations, views, downloads:

- The [Data Citation Corpus](#) aggregates data citations to datasets with DOIs and accession numbers.
- The [DataCite Commons](#) portal lists citations for datasets with DOIs, and counts of views & downloads. where available.
- Some repositories – such as [NeuroMorpho.Org](#), [Zenodo](#) or [ICPSR](#) – provide citation counts for the datasets they host.

Here are some examples of possible CV styles:

For datasets deposited in data repositories and assigned a PID (e.g. a DOI):

Minimal:

DataCite, & Make Data Count. (2025). Data Citation Corpus Data File (v4.1) [Data set]. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16901115>. **Annotated:**

DataCite, & Make Data Count. (2025). Data Citation Corpus Data File (v4.1) [Data set]. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16901115>.

Role: Project coordinator; Data type: collection of metadata records; Availability: CC0 license; Use and reuse: The different versions of the collection have had 6,900 views and have been downloaded over 1,200 times. Contribution: The dataset provides the latest available collection of data citations (910 million), bringing together citations available from different sources and for different types of data identifiers into a single open collection.

Qualitative outline:

DataCite, & Make Data Count. (2025). Data Citation Corpus Data File (v4.1) [Data set]. DataCite. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16901115>.

The Data Citation Corpus provides an aggregate of citations to datasets, bringing together for the first time datasets with DOIs and accession numbers, and enabling analyses into the use of data as part of publications broader than any other existing collection. The dataset draws on collaborations with the infrastructure provider Europe PMC and foundations including Chan Zuckerberg Initiative and Aligning Science Across Parkinson's. The dataset has had substantial community uptake, it has been downloaded over 1,200 times, and has been explored as part of meta-research into data practices and in the academic and private sector, providing for example a data source for the last State of Open Data report.

For data and/or code in active versioning and made available via platforms like GitHub, DataLad, or OSF:

Minimal:

Holford, D. L., Kempe, V., Holcombe, A. O., Puebla, I., Patel, J., Smout, C., & McLean, J. F. (2021, April 7). Testing of Pre-print Review Rubric on Student Sample. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/X9UTN>

Annotated:

Holford, D. L., Kempe, V., Holcombe, A. O., Puebla, I., Patel, J., Smout, C., & McLean, J. F. (2021, April 7). Testing of Pre-print Review Rubric on Student Sample. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/X9UTN>

Role: Conceptualization, writing; Data type: self-reported data; Availability: CC BY license; Use and reuse: The dataset was created as part of a study to develop a tool to support training students in peer review of preprints, it was used as part of that research and has also informed updates to the curriculum of the course where the tool was applied. Contribution: The dataset provides results on the evaluation of preprints using a newly developed rubric to guide peer review, it provides results on the implementation of peer review as an authentic assessment task for undergraduate students.

Qualitative outline:

Holford, D. L., Kempe, V., Holcombe, A. O., Puebla, I., Patel, J., Smout, C., & McLean, J. F. (2021, April 7). Testing of Pre-print Review Rubric on Student Sample. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/X9UTN>

The dataset provides results on the evaluation of preprints using a newly developed rubric to guide peer review. It provides results on the implementation of peer review as an authentic assessment task for undergraduate students, and also on the comparison of review evaluation between students and expert reviewers. It is one of scarce datasets available with results on preprint review contents, and it has been applied to inform updates to the tasks included in the course where the rubric was tested.

While these examples focus on datasets and code, similar approaches can be applied to outputs in the humanities, such as digital editions, archival datasets, or community-curated resources.

03

Guidance for Review Committees

Evaluating data and non-traditional research outputs

Members of review committees should strive for consistency in evaluating diverse forms of scholarship, applying the same rigor and openness to data and software as they would to traditional publications. As part of their evaluation of research contributions, reviewers should consider applying the following:

- Recognize data, software, and other digital research outputs as standalone contributions.
- When assessing research productivity, consider the diversity of outputs, especially those that foster collaboration and community use.
- Evaluate impact using a range of metrics including reuse, FAIR compliance, community feedback, and integration into further research.
- Use candidate-provided statements to understand the scholarly value and context of data-focused work.

Questions for reviewers to consider

- What forms of data does the candidate make available (raw, processed, or both)?
- To what extent does the candidate follow the FAIR principles for the data they produce?
- How has the candidate addressed any relevant ethical considerations about the creation, analysis or sharing of their data?
- How does the candidate's shared data contribute to the reproducibility of their work?
- How does the candidate's work contribute to the infrastructure or culture of open science?
- Have the candidate's datasets been used, cited, recommended, or led to further collaboration?
- Has the candidate played a leadership role in data production, management, or policy development?

Guidance for letters of recommendation from external reviewers

The template below provides text that can be included in communications to external reviewers requesting letters of recommendation, to encourage them to provide assessments on the applicant's data contributions and open research outputs.

We appreciate your independent assessment of the candidate's research contributions and standing in the field. Please note that the university's process seeks to evaluate the rigor and quality of the candidates' work, as well as their adoption of open scholarship practices. As part of your letter, we invite you to comment on the researcher's contributions accounting for publications as well as open research outputs such as datasets, software, code, workflows or protocols. This may include:

- *The candidate's practices in sharing their data and other outputs openly, where this is ethically and legally permitted*
- *The degree to which the candidate's datasets and other open outputs are reused, cited, or engaged with by the community*
- *Observations on whether and how the researcher's practices for open scholarship support the rigor and/or reproducibility of their research*
- *Observations on whether and how the researcher's practices for open scholarship address existing needs in underrepresented communities, research infrastructure, or research culture*

Your assessment will help the institution recognize contributions that advance research rigor, openness, and community impact.

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